

FARMERS RESOURCE USE EFFICIENCY IN SORGHUM PRODUCTION IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Resource use efficiency is crucial to the development of agricultural activities in Nigeria. A few studies have been conducted in this area of economics activities as it relates to agriculture. However, this aspect of study must be properly emphasized if we wish to take agriculture from its present shabby stage to the next level. This study examined the resource use efficiency among sorghum farmers in Ifelodun Local Government Area of Kwara State, Nigeria. Suitable tools such as gross margin analysis, efficiency ratio or rate of return in investment were used for the study. Empirical results revealed that approximately 70% of the farmers were above 45 years of age, 92% were married and about 85% have been involved in sorghum farming for at least 11 years. The resource use efficiency result showed that the farm resources were inefficiently utilized for sorghum production in the study area, hence the need for adjustment of resource use. Empirical result also showed that for every ₦1 invested in sorghum production, ₦1.89 was made as revenue. This suggests that sorghum production is viable in the study area. The study recommend/encourage both farmers and policy makers to invest properly in sorghum production because of its vast usage.

KEY WORDS: resource use, efficiency, agriculture, sorghum production.

INTRODUCTION

A review of the past performance of agriculture since 1970 in Nigeria clearly shows that it contributes more than 30% of the annual Gross Domestic Product (GDP), employs about 68% of the labour force, accounts for over 70% of the non-oil exports, and provides over 80% of the food needs of the country (Adegboye, 2004).

Agriculture in Nigeria is dominated by small-scale farmers who produce about 80% of the total food requirement (Fayinka, 2004). These farmers are characterized by strong dependence on agricultural labour market, little or no forms of savings or storage facilities and cultural practices adopted are highly labour intensive (Festus, 2005; Fakayode, et al 2008).

In Nigeria, Agricultural contribution to the GDP and exports has been low since the 1980s and food imports continued to rise in value. In terms of relative importance, food import as a percentage of total imports rose from 3.5% in 1991 to 11.8% in the year 2000 (CBN, 2000; Akosile, 2003; Nyanko, 2006). Nigeria has witnessed a considerable decline in food production and a widening gap in the supply and demand brought about by population growth of about 3.5% per annum relative to food production growth of about 15% per annum (Gulai, 2000; Yai'aishe Modu, etal 2010).

By 2003, the agricultural growth rate was 2.8% (PCU/FMARD, 2004), yet this growth rate is still lower than expected. Although, opinions differ on the magnitude of Nigeria's food problem, at the national level, the main food problems are food supply deficits, poverty and uneven distribution of income in terms of ability to buy food (Ohajianya, 2004). This brought about a distortion of the labour market and distribution effects on the production of food and cash crops in the country.

The production and socio-economic characteristics of the farmers, inconsistent government policies, the poor infrastructural base, all interact and affect the agricultural sector, resulting in low production, high price of food items, inflation, under-development and poverty. If Nigerians are ready to go back to agriculture, the problem of poverty, hunger and malnutrition could be alleviated. Adequate production of most Nigeria staple crops such as sorghum which is consumed in many parts of the country, will contribute positively to the agricultural sector.

Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L moench) is one of the most important staple crops in Nigeria, and is the most important cereal food in the Northern states that covers the guinea savannah ecological zone (FAO, 2004). Sorghum production

surpasses all other crops (FMEST, 1984). In terms of food contribution, sorghum is the major cereal consumed by the majority of the population (NAERLS, 1997). In the Northern states, about 73% of the total calories intake and 52.3% of the per capital protein intake are contributed by sorghum alone (Samm, 2009).

In many parts of the world, sorghum has traditionally been used in food products and various food items, porridge, unleavened bread, cookies, couscous and malted beverages are made from this versatile grain (Anno 3, 2010, Wikipedia, 2010). Traditionally food preparation of sorghum is quite varied. Boiled sorghums are some of the simplest uses and small, corneous grains are normally desired for this type of food product. The whole grain may be ground into flour or decorticated before grinding to produce either a fine particle product or flour, which is then used in various traditional foods.

Sorghum has unique properties that make it well suited for meeting today's demand for healthy food. For example, some sorghum varieties are rich in anti-oxidants and all sorghum varieties are gluten-free, making them an attractive alternative for sufferers of wheat allergies (Samm, 2009, Anno 3, 2010).

Sorghum is also an important animal feed used in countries like the United States, Mexico etc. Good-quality sorghums are available with a nutritional feeding value that is equivalent to that of corn. In 2008/2009 season about 49.36% of sorghum production goes into feed and residual uses (USAID, 2009).

In China, sorghum is the most important ingredient for the production of distilled beverages such as Maotai. In Southern Africa, it is used to produce beer, including the local version of Guinness. It is also used in the same way as barley to produce "malt". African sorghum beer is a popular drink primarily amongst the black community for historical reasons. Sorghum beer is known by many different names in various countries across Africa, including Burukutu (Nigeria), Pombe (East Africa), Bil-bil (Cameroon) and Bjala in (Northern Sotho) (USDA 2, 2010).

Sorghum stem can be made into excellent wall board for house building, as well as biodegradable packaging. It does not accumulate static electricity, so it is also being used in packaging materials for sensitive electronic equipment (Wikipedia, 2010).

According to FAO (1995) as reported by (Samm, 2009), sorghum is one of the most drought tolerant cereal crops currently under cultivation. Its morphological and physiological characteristics contribute to its adaptability to drought conditions, including an extensive root system, waxy brooms on the leaves that reduce water loss, ability to stop growth in periods of drought and to resume when conditions are favourable, and tolerance to water-logging. The crop adapts well to different soil types and toxicities. These factors together make it an ideal crop for growing in a biotically stressful environment (ITIS, 2009).

Sorghum has a unique property that makes it well suited for food uses. Some sorghum varieties are rich in antioxidants and all sorghum varieties are gluten free, an alternative for wheat allergy sufferers (Annon 2, 2010). Sorghum is one of the most drought tolerant cereal crops currently under cultivation. It offers farmers the ability to reduce costs on irrigation and other on-farm expenses. Sorghum requires an average temperature of at least 250⁰c to produce maximum yield. In general, is a very competitive crop and does well in competing with weeds in narrow rows (FAOSTAT, 2010).

Sorghum is a very high nitrogen feeding crop. Its growth habit is similar to that of maize. It has a waxy coating on its leaves and stems which helps to keep water in the plant even in intense heat (Annon 2, 2010). The leaves and grain of sorghum are use for livestock feeds and stalks for thatching houses and making fences. In Nigeria, according to NRC (1996), sorghum has greater untapped potential than any other crop. It even postulated that if the twentieth century was the century of rice, wheat and maize, then the twenty first century could become the century of sorghum.

The efficiency of a firm refers to its success in producing as large amount of output as possible given a set of inputs. Therefore, to determine the efficiency of any particular firm, there is need for efficiency measurement through the production factor input processes. This measurement has received considerable attention from both theoretical and applied economists. From a theoretical point of view, there has been a spirited exchange about their relative importance of the various components of firm efficiency (Leibenstein and Comanor 1969,

Leibernstein 1996). From an applied perspective, measuring efficiency is important because this is the first step in a process that might lead to substantial resource savings. These resource savings have important implications for both policy formulations and firm management (Bravo-Ureta and Rieger 1991).

The paper is a contributory literature on resource use efficiency of agricultural activities in developing countries. The objectives are to; examine the social economic characteristics, gross margin analysis, measure the resource use efficiency and identify problems associated with sorghum production.

Research Questions

- (i) What are the socio-economic characteristics that affect sorghum production?
- (ii) Are resources efficiently utilized in sorghum production?
- (iii) How viable is sorghum production in the study area?
- (iv) What are the constraints in sorghum production?

METHODOLOGY

This study was carried out in Ifelodun Local Government area of Kwara State, Nigeria. Ifelodun is the largest Local Government Area in Kwara State with an estimated population of about 206,042 and an estimated total land area of about 3,435 km² (NPC, 2006, KWSMI, 2002). The area is located between latitude 7^o 45N and 9^o30N and longitude 2^o 30E and 6^o 35E.

It is characterized by dry and wet season. The annual rainfall ranges between 1000mm and 1500mm. Average temperatures between 30^oc and 35^oc and humidity range from 35% to 60%. The major source of livelihood and occupation of the people in the area is farming. Farming is traditional in nature with emphasis on the cultivation of crops such as sorghum, cassava, yam, maize and melon (KWSMI, 2002, Mohammed, 2008). Sorghum is majorly grown among farmers in the area; this informed the choice of the local government area.

Sampling Technique

A reconnaissance survey was first conducted with the assistance of the extension staff of the Agriculture Department of the local government area to identify farmers who grow sorghum on their farm and/intercrop mixture.

A two stage random sampling technique was used in selecting the sample for the study. The first stage involved the random selection of 74 villages and towns from the 8 districts in the local government area using the result from the reconnaissance survey and the Kwara State ADP village listing as sample frame.

The second stage involved a random selection of sorghum farming households in each village. A total of two hundred and twenty six (226) farming households were selected and interviewed for the study.

Data Collection

The source of data used for this study was basically primary data. This involved the use of an interview schedule with a well designed structured questionnaires administered to the farmers. The secondary information were however, obtained from textbooks, internet, journals, past projects, etc.

Data were collected based on the socio-economic variables such as age, farm size, gender, educational status, income, costs and returns and constraint faced by the farmers. The response of those farmers forms the primary data used.

Analytical Technique

The analytical tools that were used for this include descriptive statistics, gross margin analysis, production function and resource use efficiency

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics employed includes frequencies and percentages ratios. This was used to analyze the socio-economic characteristics of the farmer as well as the constraints associated with sorghum production.

Gross margin analysis

Gross margin analysis is by definition the different between the gross farm income and total variable cost (Olukosi and Erhabor, 1988). Normally, gross margin analysis is used to test the effects of changes that do not alter the fixed cost of production, especially the cost of land and other durable factors. It is used to determine the potential profitability and effect on farmer's farm income. It has the advantage of being simple as well as useful in the analysis of the profitability of small farms that have small fixed costs (Samm, 2009). The gross margin analysis was estimated from costs and returns in sorghum production.

Gross margin model is expressed as follows:

$$GM = TR - TVC$$

Where:

GM = Gross margin (₦/ha)

TR = Total revenue or total value of output from the sorghum enterprise (₦/ha). It is the product of average output per hectare multiplied by the market price. The price used was open market price of the year 2010.

TVC = Total variable cost or the costs that are specific in producing (sorghum) output (₦/ha). TVC varies according to output and are incurred on variable inputs. This includes cost of inputs like seeds, fertilizer, and harvesting, processing, labour cost (hired/family).

Analysis of Resource use Efficiency

Resource use efficiency was obtained from the production function analysis. Efficiency is generally defined as the quantity of output (Y) per unit of input (X) used in the production process, that is, the average physical productivity (APP).

In order to ascertain whether resources were efficiently utilized, the marginal value product (MVP) of the variable inputs used was computed and compared with their input prices. The following ratio was used to compute the efficiency of resource use.

$$R = \frac{MVP}{MFC}$$

Where:

R = Efficiency ratio

MVP = Marginal value product (value added to sorghum output due to the use of additional unit of input)

MFC = Marginal factor cost (cost of unit of a particular resource).

But MVP is estimated as:

$$MVP = MPP_{xi} P_y$$

$$MPP_{xi} = \frac{\partial y}{\partial x_i}$$

MPP_{xi} is the marginal physical product of a unit of input X_i ,

P_y is the price of output.

The firm is allocatively efficient if the ratio of the marginal physical products MPP_x between all inputs equals the ratio of the input prices, i.e. $MPP_{xi}/MPP_{xj} = P_{xi}/P_{xj}$. Scale efficiency is achieved if the firm produces at a marginal cost that is the same as the price of the output. Both allocative and scale efficiency is the condition for profit maximization.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Social Economic characteristics

Farmers between the age of 46 years old and above (70%) were more involved in sorghum production (Table 1). Age is an important determinant of social – economic status of a population since people wear in energy as they advance in age. Therefore, this generally aged sorghum farmers could have negative implications on the future of sorghum cultivation in the study area. However, it is important to note that the older a farmer becomes, the better his understanding of the social, climatic and economic factors that affect farming and thus more

experienced. Sorghum production seem to be a male dominated activity in the study area as about 90.70% of the sample farmers are male. This may be due to the fact that women majors in processing. The male domination of sorghum farming as suggested in Table 1 may in turn be due to high demands of time and efforts required to work in such enterprise. This is in consonance with findings of Baiyegunhi and Fraser, (2009).

Illiteracy is one of the factors militating against agricultural development in Nigeria. The study shows that 28.30% of the sorghum farmers had no formal education, while about 62% managed to acquire primary and/ quranic education. Usually, such low literacy level does not allow the farmers to appreciate innovations in agricultural development in any given society as level of formal education attained by an individual goes a long way in shaping his personality attitude to life and adoption of new and improved practice (Sullumbe, 2004).

Table 1: Social Economic Characteristics

Variable	Description	Frequency	Percentage	Cum. Percentage
Age of Respondent	≤ 25	6	2.65	2.65
	26 - 35	14	6.19	8.85
	36 - 45	49	21.68	30.53
	≥46	157	69.47	100.00
	Total	226	100.00	
Gender	Male	205	90.70	90.70
	Female	21	9.30	100.00
	Total	226	100.00	
Education Status	No formal education	64	28.30	28.30
	Primary education	44	19.50	47.80
	Quaranic education	31	13.70	61.50
	Secondary Education	54	23.90	85.40
	Tertiary education	33	14.60	100.00
	Total	226	100.00	
Source of Fund	Personal	159	70.40	70.40
	Money lender	29	12.80	83.20
	Bank loan	14	6.20	89.40
	Cooperative	24	10.60	100.00
	Total	226	100.00	

Source: Data Analysis, 2010.

Education is regarded as an investment in human capital, which is able to raise the skill and quality of the man, narrow his information gaps and increase his locative efficiency thereby leading to more productive performance.

Credit facilities were not assessable to farmers in the study area as majority of the sorghum farmers (70.40%) depend solely on their personal saving. It could be concluded that respondents in the study area do not enjoy credit facility from financial institutions, which may be as a result of lack of awareness, low literacy level, high interest rate and bureaucracy. These of course have hamper production to a large extent since loan is a crucial input used to establish and expand farm sizes.

Gross Margin

The result of the gross margin analysis is presented in Tble 2. Costs incurred on various resources used and the profits obtained from the sales of the produce were estimated based on the market price at the period under consideration (2010 farming season). A gross return was calculated by multiplying the total quantity of produce harvested by the price of output sold. The average gross return of the respondents was ₦63,409,400.00

For cost of production, total variable cost and total fixed cost were considered in order to calculate the total cost of production. The total variable cost includes cost of labour, chemicals, fertilizer and seeds while total fixed costs includes cost of renting land, and depreciation on farm tools. The straight line method, which assumed a constant rate of annual depreciation, was used to calculate the depreciation on farm tools.

The labour used consists of family, hired and group labour. The wage rate varies slightly depending on the operation to be performed on the farm. The average wage rate of ₦750.00 per man-hour was used to calculate the total labour cost. The total cost of labour accounts for 8.11% of the variable cost.

The cost incurred on chemical was ₦2,239,750.00, accounting for about 8.69% of the variable cost. This cost appears rather high due to the fact that chemicals are usually expensive during farming season.

Table 2: Gross margin and returns in investment

Item	Amount (N)	
Total Revenue		63,409,400
Labour	2,088,750	
Cost of chemicals	2,239,750	
Cost of fertilizer	17,443,200	
Cost of seed	3,981,600	
Total variable cost	25,753,300	25,753,300
Gross margin		37,656,100
Total fixed cost	7,718,900	7,718,900
Net Farm Income/Profit (NFI)		29,937,200
Rate of Return on investment (ROR)	1.89 (189%)	
Efficiency level/(RORCI)(%)	0.89 (89%)	

Source: Data Analysis, 2010.

The study revealed that most respondents engaged in poor seedlings practices resulting in low germination percentage. To overcome this problem, farmers plant more seeds in anticipation of getting high germination percentage. More often, farmers seem not to pay attention to the quantity of seed planted, just because seedlings would be thinned. Most times thinning are delayed beyond three weeks after germination which adversely affects yield.

An average market price of ₦5,000.00 per 5 kilogram of sorghum seed was used in estimating the total cost of seeds. The total cost of seed used was found to be ₦3,981,600.00, which is about 15.46%. The cost of fertilizer was as high as ₦17,443,200.00, representing 67.74% of the total cost of production. Table 2 shows that on average the total variable cost is ₦25,753,300.00 which accounts for about 76.94% of the overall production cost. The gross margin and net farm income (profit) were ₦37,656,100.00 and ₦29,937,200.00 respectively.

Resource Use Efficiency

The crucial role of efficiency in increasing agricultural output has been duly reorganized by researchers and policy maker alike.

In determining the efficiency of the inputs used, Marginal Value Product and the Marginal Factor Cost (MVP and MFC) were determined. The marginal factor cost which is the unit price for the variable inputs used in sorghum production in the study area were found to be ₦5,500.00, ₦4,500.00, ₦5000.00 and ₦850.00 for seed, farm size, fertilizer and chemical respectively. This result is as presented in Table 3.

Seed input is being employed below economic optimum level as indicated by its efficiency ratio 7.27. It is therefore rational to increase the quantity of seed as this will bring about a corresponding increase in total value product of about ₦39.96.

Fertilizer was also seen to be under utilized as shown by its value of efficiency ratio. This suggests that with other inputs held constant, increasing fertilizer by one kilogram would increase total value product by ₦9.88. Other inputs were also seen to be currently under utilized. It is therefore economical to increase the use of these inputs for optimal return in investment in the study area. Hence resource use adjustment and optimal combination of these parameters should be adopted by farmers in the study area.

Table 3: Resource use efficiency

Resource	MPP(Kg)	Unit price of input(N'000)	MVP(N'000)	MFC(N'000)	R=MVP/MFC
Seed	7.40	5.50	39.96	5.50	7.27
Farm Size	3.87	4.50	20.90	4.50	4.64
Fertilizer	1.83	5.00	9.88	5.00	1.98
Chemical	0.52	0.85	2.81	0.85	3.31

Source: Data Analysis, 2010.

Problems Affecting Sorghum Production

Profit maximization is chiefly the concern or the primary objective of farmers in production enterprise. This reasoning also applies to farmers in the study area and much more due to the fact that sorghum as a staple crop serve several purposes such as home consumption, livestock feed and residual, export crop and industrial uses and perhaps one of the most drought tolerant cereal crops currently under cultivation Annon 3, (2010).

Table 4 identified some problems affecting sorghum production in the study area. These include such problems as high cost of labour, transportation, lack of adequate fund, lack of access to extension services etc. 43.75% of respondents indentified high cost of labour as very severe. Scarcity is usually characterized by high cost of input variables of production; therefore the high cost of labour could imply unavailability of labour. Hence the amount charged per man-day was high.

Table 4: Problems/Constraints affecting sorghum production

Constraints	Severity (%)				
	VS	S	NS	Indiff.	Total
High cost of labour	43.75	37.50	18.75	0.00	100.00
High cost of transportation	44.64	37.50	16.96	0.89	100.00
Inadequate fund	71.43	22.32	5.80	0.45	100.00
Inadequate access to Extension services	58.85	25.22	13.72	2.21	100.00
inadequate access to improved/hybrid seed	73.89	12.83	13.27	0.00	100.00
Lack of market for product	20.35	17.70	56.64	5.31	100.00
Lack of motorable road	26.79	29.91	40.63	2.68	100.00
Lack of recommended Agrochemicals	40.63	23.21	30.80	5.36	100.00
Poor pricing of sorghum products	24.11	28.57	45.09	2.23	100.00
Problems of pest and diseases	33.04	26.34	37.50	3.13	100.00

Source: Data Analysis, 2010.

The result also revealed that fund was another very severe constraint to sorghum production (71.43%). Since most of the respondents are small- scale farmers, they have low capital base and therefore cannot afford the high cost of inputs. Also, the stringent conditions and bureaucratic tendencies of formal credit institutions shy farmers away from obtaining loans to finance their farm operation.

Another problem considered as being very severe by the respondents is lack of access to improved hybrid sorghum seed. This is perceived by about 73.89% of the respondents. This may be due to non awareness, poor education and poor access to extension services,

CONCLUSION

The study revealed sorghum production is viable and can serve as a means of earning livelihood if properly invested on. Production/cultivation of this very important crop would be enhanced through improve seedling practice, proper application fertilizers and appropriate use of chemicals.

To fully tap the potential of increasing profit in sorghum production, efforts should be geared towards providing solution to identified problems. Therefore, individuals, government and non- governmental organization are encouraged to assist the farmers in order to improve sorghum production in the study area and Nigeria in general.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to efficiently utilized farm inputs in the study area, we proffer the following recommendations;

- (i) Improved/hybrid varieties of sorghum seed be made available to the farmers.
- (ii) Low cost technologies should be developed by research and allied institution to ease high cost of labour observed in the study.
- (iii) Fertilizer cost was indeed unbearable and outrageous. Therefore parties in fertilizers distribution subsidy should take note of this menace and aid sorghum production in the study area.
- (iv) Farmers should be provided with extension agents that can help them on the proper use of both allocative and scale efficiency to enhance optimum and profit maximization in the production of sorghum.

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